

Analysis of the Elastoplastic Behavior of $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ and $(+\theta/-\theta)$ Bidirectionally Fiber-Reinforced Ductile Matrix Composites in Uniaxial Loading

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with a micromechanical formulation of elastoplastic constitutive relations of composite materials. A general description without restricting geometric details of constituent phases is presented on the basis of the assumption that plastic deformation occurs uniformly within a matrix which obeys the Levy-von Mises flow rule. Explicit results can be obtained for specific phase geometries in which reinforcing phases are in the form of general ellipsoids that orient in two (or more) specific material directions. As an illustration, numerical results are shown for two different types of bidirectional carbon fiber/aluminum composites — one corresponding to the "cross-ply" and the other to the "angle-ply" configuration — subjected to uniaxial tension along one of the principal material directions. A notable feature of the results is that anisotropy of the composite deformation behavior is greatly enhanced in the post-yield elastoplastic range as compared with that in the pre-yield elastic range.

INTRODUCTION

Concurrently with expanding application of fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP), there has been increasing interest in metal-matrix composites reinforced with strong metallic wires or nonmetallic filaments as advanced structural materials especially for aerospace applications. Advantages of fiber-reinforced metals (FRM) stem from a number of superior intrinsic properties of metallic substances as compared with polymeric ones, which include ductility and toughness, nonflammability, resistance to moisture, electrical and thermal conductivity and ability to be heat treated. For example, considerable improvements in transverse mechanical properties of unidirectional boron/epoxy and carbon/epoxy can be achieved through the replacement of epoxy by aluminum.

Several problems that are of less importance in FRP technology have to be solved in order to promote practical use of FRM in advanced structural components. These include a complicated interfacial problem due to physicochemical interactions between the composite constituents occurring during service and/or fabrication at elevated temperatures. The difficulty in mass production also is the problem that must be overcome. Besides these materials scientist and engineer-side problems, structure designers are forced to have a deep understanding of inelastic, or more correctly, elastoplastic behavior of FRM resulting from yield-

ing of the ductile matrix. This is because efficient design often dictates use of these materials with the matrix in a yielded condition. Knowledge of elastoplastic composite behavior is apparently deficient in comparison with that of purely elastic behavior.

Different approaches can be made for an analytical study of the problem of elastoplastic behavior of composite materials. According to Adams in his review article [1], these approaches are classified, depending on the level of modeling accuracy, into (1) simple model analyses and (2) rigorous (numerical) analyses. Approaches of the first class are defined as those which utilize such material models as to involve either crude or sophisticated approximations to physical reality. Such models include strength-of-materials models [2], concentric cylinder models [3-6] and self-consistent models [7-9]. An approach developed by Mulhern, Rogers and Spencer [10] and adopted by Prager [11], though not cited in [1], may also fall within this category. In this approach the assumed plastic inextensibility of the reinforcing fiber is regarded as a geometric constraint imposed on a von Mises material. This approach is of particular interest among others in the sense that it can handle somewhat complicated situations in which reinforcing fiber arrays are multidirectional and applied loading is arbitrarily polyaxial. However, the model material utilized is in itself a homogeneous continuum, i.e., the inhomogeneous nature of actual composites is not explicitly recognized, so that the approach is not micromechanical but macromechanical. Approaches of the second class are defined as: — those which satisfy the mathematical laws of analytical mechanics and at the same time accurately model the known physical constraints associated with the material characteristics of the individual constituents and their geometric arrangement within the composite. Work on this line can be seen, for example, in a paper by Adams [12]. In practice, such "rigorous" continuum mechanics analyses first require the establishment of a specific filament packing geometry, e.g. mostly a periodic regular array of filaments of circular cross section, and then solutions under appropriated boundary conditions are obtained with respect to a representative repeating unit cell by using a numerical solution technique of some type, e.g. the finite element method. At the present time an analysis of this type alone is capable of providing reliable information about local stresses and strains. However, although the basic methodology is now in hand, these approaches usually require a large storage capacity digital computer and extraordinarily long computation time when applied to reduced symmetry problems.

The investigation presented here is concerned with a micromechanical formulation of elastoplastic constitutive relations of those composites in which elastic reinforcements (inclusions) in the form of general ellipsoids are embedded in an elastic-perfectly plastic matrix in such a way as to orient in two or more specific material directions. Individual inclusions of one group (which all orient in one specific material direction) are assumed to be identical in shape and have the same (either isotropic or anisotropic) elastic constants but can differ in these respects from inclusions of any other groups. This implies that our approach is equally applicable to hybrid composites. Moreover, no restriction is imposed on applied loading regimes (provided that the resulting applied stress field within the composite is macroscopically uniform), so that our approach is capable of analysing asymmetric deformation behavior occurring when loading axes do not coincide with principal material directions, e.g. deformation of unidirectional composites in off-axis tension. In most practical FRM the volume fraction of reinforcing fibers is not small, i.e., individual fibers are closely spaced and interact mutually. This interaction effect is, in a scientific as well as a practical sense, of great importance and taken into consideration at the same level of approximation as in our previous work on related subjects [13-19].

In the following, we shall first give a general description of elastoplastic constitutive relations of composites without restricting geometric details. The only assumption to be made is that plastic deformation occurs uniformly throughout the matrix obeying the Levy-von Mises flow rule while the reinforcing phase is not plastically deformable. In such circumstances, it is important to recognize that stresses in the constituent phases are due, in one part, to externally applied loading and, in another part, to internal generation as a result of accumulation

of dislocations at the reinforcement-matrix interface. Constituent phase stresses in the latter part are proportional, when averaged over the respective phases, to the amount of plastic strain of the matrix and hence, the elastic energy stored in the composite is given as a quadratic expression of the matrix plastic strain. The constitutive relations of composites in isothermal conditions are deduced by utilizing a certain well-established thermodynamic relationship, i.e., $\epsilon_{ij} = -(\partial G / \partial \sigma_{ij})_T$. Detailed results can be obtained for the specific phase geometry mentioned above. As an illustration, results will then be given for bidirectionally fiber-reinforced composites subjected to uniaxial tension. The bidirectional fiber arrays are set in the directions of either 0° and 90° or $+\theta$ and $-\theta$ to one of the rectangular coordinate axes. Both types of fiber arrangement are quite common as is met in the so-called cross-ply and angle-ply configurations in laminated fibrous composites although individual plies are not recognized in our material model. Of particular interest is anisotropic deformation behavior of these composites exhibiting three-dimensional orthotropy, which can be well represented in terms of strain ratios conformed to the Poisson ratio in the case of purely elastic behavior.

A GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF ELASTOPLASTIC CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONS

The formulation presented in this section begins with the recognition of a certain thermodynamic relationship, established in the case of purely elastic deformation, to be valid even when the deformation of a specimen includes an unrecoverable (plastic) part as well as the recoverable (elastic) one. The relationship of interest here is:

$$\epsilon_{ij} = -(\partial G / \partial \sigma_{ij})_T \quad (1)$$

where G denotes the Gibbs free energy of the system (specimen), i.e., the Helmholtz free energy of the specimen plus the potential energy of any external loading mechanism [20], and T the temperature. σ_{ij} and ϵ_{ij} usually stand for the stress and strain respectively in homogeneous elastic deformation. However, they should be interpreted, in the case concerned, as effective or macroscopically averaged values of the stress and total strain, the latter including not only the elastic but also the plastic part. The following is noteworthy here to avoid confusion. In deriving Eq. (1) one has to introduce the concept of a reversible process. Needless to say, plastic deformation of solids actually involves in itself an irreversible nature. Notwithstanding, a reversible process can be imagined for the situation of interest here in so far as the size/shape change of the specimen due to plastic deformation is discussed.

When our specimen undergoes purely elastic deformation, the Gibbs free energy per unit volume of the specimen is given as $G = -(1/2)S_{ij}\bar{\sigma}_i\bar{\sigma}_j$ and substitution of this expression into Eq. (1) — $\bar{\epsilon}_i = -(\partial G / \partial \bar{\sigma}_i)_T$ — leads to the well-known elastic constitutive relations of the form $\bar{\epsilon}_i = S_{ij}\bar{\sigma}_j$ where $\bar{\sigma}_i$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_i$ are the macroscopic stress and total (in this case elastic) strain of the composite respectively and S_{ij} denotes the effective elastic compliance matrix of the composite. (Here and in the following, the usual contracted notation is used for stresses and strains; the range on subscripts is from 1 to 6 unless otherwise specified.) When, however, the unrecoverable part of deformation as a result of generation of a homogeneous plastic strain ϵ^P_j within the matrix is included, G can be written in the form

$$G = -\frac{1}{2}S_{ij}\bar{\sigma}_i\bar{\sigma}_j + \frac{1}{2}L_{ij}\epsilon^P_i\epsilon^P_j - P_{ij}\bar{\sigma}_i\epsilon^P_j \quad (2)$$

where L_{ij} and P_{ij} are constants depending on constituent elastic properties and geometric factors and can be evaluated, as will be seen later, for the specific composite system mentioned earlier. Accordingly, the elastoplastic constitutive relations of the composite have the form

$$\bar{\epsilon}_i = S_{ij}\bar{\sigma}_j + P_{ij}\epsilon^P_j \quad (3)$$

where the second term on the right-hand side represents the macroscopic plastic strain of the composite.

The description so far presented is nothing but a formal one in the sense that the constitutive relations derived [Eq. (3)] contain unknown ϵP_i 's. Our next subject, therefore, is to determine all ϵP_i 's in a given state of applied loading. We first write ϵP_i such that

$$\epsilon P_i = \lambda_i \epsilon P \quad (|\lambda_i| \leq 1 \text{ and } \epsilon P > 0) \quad (4)$$

Here, ϵP and a set of λ_i 's are interpreted as quantities describing the amount and mode of plastic deformation of the matrix, respectively. Similarly,

$$\bar{\sigma}_i = \tau_i \bar{\sigma} \quad (|\tau_i| \leq 1 \text{ and } \bar{\sigma} > 0) \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}$ and a set of τ_i 's, simply describing the magnitude and direction of the macroscopic stress vector in stress hyperspace respectively, are prescribed quantities depending on applied loading conditions. Then, Eq. (2) becomes

$$G = -\frac{1}{2} S_{ij} \tau_i \tau_j (\bar{\sigma})^2 + \frac{1}{2} L_{ij} \lambda_i \lambda_j (\epsilon P)^2 - P_{ij} \tau_i \lambda_j \bar{\sigma} \epsilon P \quad (6)$$

The variation of G associated with the variation of ϵP , i.e., $\delta G = (L_{ij} \lambda_i \lambda_j \epsilon P - P_{ij} \tau_i \lambda_j \bar{\sigma}) \delta \epsilon P$, should satisfy the inequality of $\delta G \leq 0$ since plastic deformation actually involves an irreversible, or a frictional, process. This inequality is convertible to the equality of the form

$$\delta G + \delta WP = 0 \quad (\delta WP \geq 0) \quad (7)$$

and when plastic deformation of the matrix is assumed to obey the Levy-von Mises flow rule, δWP can be expressed as

$$\delta WP = V_m Y_0 (\sqrt{2/3} \lambda) |\delta \epsilon P| \quad (8)$$

with

$$\lambda \equiv [\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_3^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\lambda_4^2 + \lambda_5^2 + \lambda_6^2)]^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

where Y_0 is the yield strength of the matrix in uniaxial tensile loading and V_m is the volume fraction of the matrix. We therefore obtain a relation between ϵP and $\bar{\sigma}$:

$$\epsilon P = (P_{ij} \tau_i \lambda_j \bar{\sigma} - k \lambda) / (L_{ij} \lambda_i \lambda_j) \quad (k \equiv \pm \sqrt{2/3} V_m Y_0) \quad (10)$$

where the positive sign appearing in the definition of k refers to the forward straining ($\delta \epsilon P > 0$) and the negative sign to the backward straining ($\delta \epsilon P < 0$). Elimination of ϵP in Eq. (6) by the use of Eq. (10) yields

$$G = [-(P_{ij} \tau_i \lambda_j)^2 (\bar{\sigma})^2 + k^2 \lambda^2] / (2 L_{ij} \lambda_i \lambda_j) + G_0 \quad (11)$$

where $G_0 = -(1/2) S_{ij} \tau_i \tau_j (\bar{\sigma})^2$. It can be seen from this expression that the composite undergoing elastoplastic deformation in a given applied loading condition can have different Gibbs free energy values depending on various modes of plastic deformation of the matrix. Among these the actual one should be uniquely determined and this is done by finding the set of λ_i values that yields the smallest value of G . It should be noted that this minimization has to be done subject to a constraint condition

$$\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 = 0 \quad (12)$$

which results from plastic incompressibility of the matrix. This implies that our formulation of elastoplastic constitutive relations of composites has been completed.

APPLICATION TO SPECIFIC PHASE GEOMETRIES

In practising analyses of the problem of elastoplastic behavior of composites following the procedure presented in the preceding section, the matrices, S_{ij} , L_{ij} and P_{ij} , appearing in the expression of G [Eq. (2)] need to be determined from a micromechanics point of view. This in general is intractable unless one assumes specific phase geometries in which reinforcing phases have such simple shapes as spheres and cylinders. Of great usefulness in this respect is Eshelby's work [21,

22] on the transformation and inhomogeneity problems of an ellipsoidal inclusion. (Explicit results given therein are within the framework of isotropic elasticity; corresponding results based on anisotropic elasticity are also available [23,24].) Eshelby showed us an elegant "equivalent inclusion" method which makes the above matrices exactly calculable provided that elastic interaction of inclusions can be disregarded. For further reference, see the work by Tanaka and Mori [25], who utilized Eshelby's work in developing a theory of the work hardening of materials containing dilute concentrations of plastically nondeforming particles and fibers. In our probe, however, consideration of the interaction effect is indispensable and this can be made, in an approximate manner, by exploiting Mori and Tanaka's "average interaction strain" analysis [26] along with Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method [23,24]. By the "average interaction strain" is meant an average (elastic) strain induced in the matrix when a large number of misfitting ellipsoids with the same elastic constants as those of the matrix are embedded in the matrix of finite extent. This kind of approach to account for the interaction effect has been used in a series of our papers [13-19] and recently adopted by other investigators [27,28]. Details of the calculation procedure can be seen by reference to these papers and are not given here.

As an illustration by the present method of elastoplastic composite behavior analysis, some results obtained for $[+\theta/-\theta]$ and $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ bidirectional carbon fiber/aluminum composites (CFRAl) subjected to uniaxial tension along one of the principal material directions (the x_3 direction in Fig. 1) are shown in Figs. 2 through 5. Input values are

	Al Matrix	Carbon Fiber
Young's Modulus, E (GN/m ²)	71.5	235.2
Poisson's Ratio, ν	0.33	0.17
Yield Stress, Y_0 (MN/m ²)	35.0	
Volume Fraction, V	0.6	0.4

No account is taken of the elastic anisotropy of carbon fibers which is strongly dependent on a degree of orienting of hexagonal crystallites. The shape of carbon fibers is assumed to be an extremely long prolate spheroid. The indicated value (0.4) for the fiber volume fraction V_f of course means the total fiber content by fractional volume; the partition of this value to the respective groups of fibers orienting in two different directions is made equally for composites of the $[+\theta/-\theta]$ type whereas unequal partitions are considered here for composites of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ type. In the latter case, we thus define a fiber partition fraction η such that

$$\eta = V_{f,90^\circ} / (V_{f,0^\circ} + V_{f,90^\circ}).$$

Note that $\eta = 0$ and $\eta = 1$ imply unidirectional composites, the former being the case of longitudinal tensile loading with the latter for the case of transverse tensile loading. The situation is also similar for composites of the $[+\theta/-\theta]$ type, i.e., the cases where $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$.

As is naturally expected, these composites generally exhibit certain anisotropy in their deformation behavior, which can now be well represented in terms of

Fig. 1 Coordinates and specimen geometry.

strain ratios, $-\bar{\epsilon}_{11}/\bar{\epsilon}_{33}$ and $-\bar{\epsilon}_{22}/\bar{\epsilon}_{33}$, defined in the coordinate system shown in Fig. 1. The results for the two types of composites are shown in Figs. 2 and 3, where the horizontal axis is given as the applied tensile stress σ normalized by the composite yield stress σ_0 [cf. Fig. 4]. A notable feature here is that the strain ratios sharply change with the initiation of matrix yielding, approaching to those asymptotic values which vary in a wider range as compared with the purely elastic case. The stress-dependent strain ratios in the post-yield elastoplastic range imply that the derived composite stress-strain curves in this range is non-linear and this is particularly so for the stress-strain behavior other than in the loading direction. Virtually linear stress-strain behavior in the loading direction observed in all cases is a consequence that in the present analysis ac-

Fig. 2 (Above) Strain ratios, (a) $-\bar{\epsilon}_{11}/\bar{\epsilon}_{33}$ and (b) $-\bar{\epsilon}_{22}/\bar{\epsilon}_{33}$, as a function of normalized applied tensile stress σ/σ_0 for composites of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ type.

Fig. 3 (Below) As in Fig. 2, except for composites of the $[+\theta/-\theta]$ type.

Fig. 4 (Left) Variation of composite yield stress σ_0 with η and θ .

Fig. 5 (Right) Variations of composite "Young's modulus (E_I)" and "tangent modulus (E_{II})" with η and θ .

tual nonlinear strain-hardening behavior of the matrix as well as nonuniform development of the yielded zone within the matrix is not taken into account. The former effect, however, can easily be incorporated into the analysis by regarding Y_0 in Eq. (8) as a given function of ϵP , e.g., a function of the form, $Y_0 + K(\epsilon P)^m$, where K and m are material constants. On the other hand, our model in principle excludes the latter effect and therefore the composite flow stress values derived are overestimated especially in the early stages of elastoplastic deformation. The pseudolinear post-yield stress-strain curves in the loading direction can be well represented by their slopes or "tangent modulus (E_{II})" values and these values are compared with "Young's modulus (E_I)" values (slopes of the pre-yield portion of stress-strain curves) in Fig. 5. Enhanced anisotropy in the elastoplastic range can also be seen from this figure. Finally, it is interesting to note that both E_I and E_{II} values for $\theta = 0^\circ$ ($\eta = 0$), which are for unidirectional composites in longitudinal tensile loading, agree with those of "rule-of-mixtures" predictions.

In conclusion, the proposed analytical method based on energetics is very powerful for the study of (isothermal) elastoplastic constitutive relations of composite materials; this is particularly so when one wishes to handle more complicated and less symmetric problems.

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